

The Power of Resistance: A Comparative Study on Canadian Literature and Pakistan Literature

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Abstract

The present paper traces the turbulent process of extremism and violence in Afghanistan and Pakistan. The ill-effects of violence is struggled by people of Afghanistan and Pakistan. The true personalities of war area are highly paralleled with the protagonists, Parvana and Malala. Both are the protagonist of the selected study. Their life reveals the truth that people are really waiting to report and strive hard to attain the stage of revival. The present paper has compared the novel written by Deborah Ellis and autobiography written by Malala Yousafzai based on the aspects of surrounding, atmosphere, social milieu and the treatment of women. Both the works of art through the experience of protagonists, undergo identity negotiation and attain the stage of Becoming from the stage of being. These stories attracts the realistic mode of living and places the readers one among their society.

Comparative Literature is a literary discipline and ought to be recognised as the most important academic activity of the present era. Etymologically the term 'Comparative Literature' means any literary work or art that compares with another. Such a comparison could be in terms of structure, philosophy, vision, theme or style. A study in comparative literature ought to lead us to a more comprehensive and adequate understanding of the works and the concerned authors. Mainly, it seeks to study interactions between literatures written in various countries in various languages. The comparative study of themes is connected with mythology on the one hand and with intellectual history on the other.

This paper attempts to compare the similarities found in the painful background of Canadian Literature and Pakistan Literature. Canadian Literature includes failure and futility feature heavily as themes in many notable works. Another notable theme is humour, many serious subjects are often laced with humour. Some of the famous Canadian writers are Michael Ondaatje who was the first to receive the Booker Prize for *The English Patient*, next comes Margaret Atwood and Yann Mortel. By documenting local experience and using the local voice, they fostered regional and national culture.

The basis of this paper is to compare two different works of art with their similar aspects; on such grounds it is essential to look after

the Pakistan Literature and its rich sources. Pakistan has sometimes been considered a land beret of world-class authors. Dr. Alamgir Hashmi introduced the term Pakistani Literature in English with preface to his pioneering book *Pakistani Literature: The Contemporary English Writers*. The early success of Pakistan Literature was marked by Ahmed Ali, Zulfikar Ghose, Bapsi Sidhwa.

The choice of study chosen for this paper is the novel written by Deborah Ellis entitled *The Breadwinner* and an autobiography written by Malala Yousafzai entitled *I am Malala*. Women play roles in our society than no other time period has ever allowed but still in most parts of the world the equality of women are highly subjugated in the name of culture, myth, traditions and dictatorship. The extreme controversial infrastructure still prevails around the world. Known things are ever trustworthy. Likewise two works of art which are highly similar in many interesting aspects as injustice, flaws in social life, violation of humanity and striving hard to attain peaceful life.

The Breadwinner by Deborah Ellis and *I am Malala* by Malala Yousafzai paves way the right path. These two books are nationally and internationally acclaimed. Ellis and Malala as writers have taken their narrative liberty to bring out the hidden facts of two warfare countries, Afghanistan and Pakistan. Both the genres are not new to literature but both of them have their own significant feature to intertwine the realism and the fictional qualities.

In the novel *The Breadwinner*, Ellis gives out the true incident that took place in Afghanistan. Besides being a writer, Ellis is also an anti-war activist. In 1997, she went to Afghanistan to assist the refugee camps. When she worked in the refugee camps, she made an interview with an Afghan mother. She got the inspiration to write *The Breadwinner* from this interview. Simultaneously on the other hand, Malala Yousafzai wrote a memoir based on the true incident that happened in Pakistan. This course of study between Canadian and Pakistan literature involves theoretically and practically informed comparative studies of the changing facets of contemporary culture in Afghanistan and Pakistan.

In *The Breadwinner*, the story begins in Kabul market place where Parvana, the woman protagonist of the novel helps her father and her family to run their daily life. Women are forbidden from attending school, they have to wear burqas to cover their bodies and faces. Parvana is forced to find ways to support her family, by hiding her birth identity as a girl and reveals herself as a twelve year old boy. Her father is arrested by the war groups, so Parvana had to find bread to her family, since women are forbidden to enter the outside world rather stay inside. Parvana feels a sense of hope. This novel for the readers explores the harsh realities of life for girls and women in modern day Afghanistan.

I am Malala an autobiography by Malala Yousafzai is a wonderful book that succeed at multiple levels. It is a warm tale of a talented girl Malala herself and her family, set against the complex and shifting events of Pakistani politics and the native Pashtun culture. The autobiography engages the account of one girl's life in the wild, beautiful and contested Swat valley region of Pakistan. Malala Yousafzai refused to be silenced and fought for her right to education. *I am Malala* will make anyone to believe in the power of a single person's voice to instill a change in the world.

The chief cooperation between these two works of art is the true incidents of life under the war surround areas. It shows how a woman struggles to make a place in a society where she is not accepted as an equal. Both the protagonists shed light on the fact that women have the abilities to face the cruelties of life at their very young age.

Dehumanization of Parvana in *The Breadwinner* or Malala in *I am Malala* can be literally noted as a single event but in most cases they are bold and genuine representatives of the cluster of events. It can be precisely stated that women inside and outside the novel are living a never ending horror. The exploration of women of Afghanistan and Pakistan are well said in both the works of

art. The harsh restrictions lay upon Parvana seems to be terrific that even three year old girl cannot walk in the street for only reason of being a girl child. Parvana in *The Breadwinner* and Malala in *I am Malala* were much concerned about their particular view more naturally than necessarily, as it replicates the original.

From the initial till the end Parvana could do things successful only because of the family's encouragement particularly her father. "You are all brave women. You are all inheritors of the courage Malali... We can win this battle" (*The Breadwinner* 29). He narrates the historical events taken place in Afghanistan and shares numerous thought provoking ideas to Parvana. Parvana had grown up with his stories, which made her a very good student. It is her father who poured in bravery to Parvana.

Simultaneously on the other hand, for many Pakistani's it was gloomy days when a daughter is born. This thought was strictly unseen in the mind of Malala's father because he wants his daughter to be an empowering woman. Malala in *I am Malala* has been vigorously advocated by her father in educating herself and be a successful activist. Malala bloomed like a bright flower in her hometown. She went to school and tasted the delight of education. Education was the only weapon to be used by Malala in building herself solely.

Parvana and Malala think that man is free to think and act. Psychologically interpreting Parvana and Malala emphasizes the idea that, individual man will be responsible for his commitments. Though their lives are full of uncertainties, the new philosophy guides them for progress. In fact, Kierkegaard, coined the term Existentialism, to emphasize on man's authentic mode of life. He believed in the existence and benevolence of God but not in the existence of religion. He said man, for better life, must pursue either aesthetic life seeking happiness in family, business and profession. He advised people to face life. Finally he says man is all in all. Parvana and Malala are individually interrelated with their self, society and surrounding to become successful.

Note: This paper has adhered to VIII Edition of MLA Handbook for Writers of Research Papers.

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